

Structural Changes in Lead Phosphate Glasses doped with Vanadyl

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A series of lead phosphate glass doped with vanadyl were prepared by a single -step process from PbO and $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$. In these glasses the transition metal ion as vanadyl VO^{2+} ion derived from $\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as VO^{2+} (VS) doped and VO^{2+} (VP) is used as another dopant derived from V_2O_5 . A thorough Knowledge of optical properties of transparent glasses will enable successful utilization of glasses for optical applications such as windows, filters and lasers. The optical absorption spectra of these glasses in the ultra-violet region have been recorded. The results obtained on the electronic absorption spectra observed to d-d bands. The VO^{2+} ions along with the double-bonded oxygen exist in a molecular complex which is identified as VO_5 polyhedra in lead phosphate glass network. As the Pbo content in the glass increases, structural changes take place in the network. The IR Spectra of these glasses were also presented with the results.

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